

**A STUDY OF INTERPERSONAL AND INTRAPERSONAL INTELLIGENCE IN
D.T.ED.COLLEGES AT LATUR CITY**

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Abstract:

The development of teacher training is depending on the policy of education and the implication of that policy. According to the U.S. department of Education, "Research confirms those teachers are the single most important factor in raising student achievement." Teacher is going to prepare a student, a citizen who built country. A variety of training programs are organized for the development of teacher's ability. The professional development of teacher is two types i.e. pre-service and In-service training which are organized by various institutions. The prime objectives of pre service training (in this study .D.T.Ed.is pre service training) to prepare educators for tomorrow.To developing the teacher education we must think new theories of learning, teaching and the new horizons in education.

Introduction:-

The theory of Multiple Intelligence is the one of the new horizons in teaching learning process. Dr.Howard Gardner is a professor at Harvard University and the author of many books and articles. His theory of multiple intelligences has challenged about a single measure of intelligence.

Dr.Gardner specifies the original seven intelligence in his book **Frimes of mind**.

- 1) Linguistic

- 2) Logical-mathematical
- 3) Musical
- 4) Spatial
- 5) Bodily kinaesthetic
- 6) Interpersonal
- 7) Intrapersonal

To identify the multiple intelligence of teacher educator is the good way of enhancing the quality of teaching, because each educator have his own learning style and the own type of intelligence. If we recognize teacher educators multiple intelligence to utilize specialized knowledge, skills for the benefit of his students. Therefore the present research paper is devoted to discuss the educators intrapersonal and interpersonal intelligence it will be helpful to know the teacher educator's intelligence and his strength.

Key words: *Intrapersonal, Interpersonal intelligence*

Interpersonal intelligence:

It means that you understand what people need to work well. Individuals with this intelligence communicate effectively and empathize easily with others, and may be either leaders or followers.

Intrapersonal intelligence:-

This refers to having a deep understanding of the self; what your strengths/weaknesses are, what makes you unique, being able to predict your own reactions/emotions

Objectives of Research:-

- 1) To study the intrapersonal intelligence and interpersonal intelligence in D.T.Ed.college students at Latur city.
- 2) To compare interpersonal and intrapersonal intelligence of girls and boys in D.T.Ed.college at Latur city.

Assumption:-

- 1) Interpersonal and intrapersonal intelligence identified with use of rating scale.
- 2) Comparison of girls and boys intelligence is possible.

Scope and limitation:-

- Researcher studies only for Intrapersonal and Interpersonal intelligence of D.T.Ed.college students.
- Research conducted in D.T.Ed.colleges at Latur city.

Sample of Research :-

College	A	B	C	D	E	F	Total Student
Boys	5	13	5	7	6	12	48
Girls	20	12	20	18	19	13	102
Total	25	25	25	25	25	25	150

Researcher selects 6 D.T.Ed.college's in Latur city by purposive sampling researcher select 25 students in each colleges and the selection of students is also purposively researcher choose 150 students as total sample to analyzing this data researcher used percentage as statistic parameter.

Research Methodology and Tool of Data Collection:-

The researcher conducted this research using survey method and study Intrapersonal and Interpersonal intelligence of D.T.Ed.college students. Present research's data collection tool was rating scale and this rating scale filled by students in D.T.Ed.college after this research Researcher got answer of his problem also knows the Intrapersonal and Interpersonal intelligence of students to identify there own intelligence and strength .Percentage statistical parameter used in present research.

Analysis of data:-

Researcher analysis his data by percentage and also compare with two variable girls and boys to compare this two researcher use column graph. The analysis is as follows.

Table No.1

Interpersonal Intelligence

Number of Boys	Percentage	No of girls	Percentage
48	72.88	102	70.26

Table No.1 shows that boy's interpersonal intelligence is 72.88% and the girl's interpersonal intelligence is 70.26%

Graph No.1

Graph also shows that percentage of boy's interpersonal intelligence is large than girl's interpersonal intelligence.

Table No. 2

Intrapersonal Intelligence

Number of Boys	Percentage	No of girls	Percentage
48	74.27	102	67.09

Table No.2 shows that boy's intrapersonal intelligence is 74.27% and the girl's intrapersonal intelligence is 67.09%

Graph No. 2

Graph also shows that percentage of boy's intrapersonal intelligence is larger than girl's intrapersonal intelligence.

Major finding of research

- 1) Boys are smarter in Interpersonal intelligence than girls.
- 2) Girls are smarter in intrapersonal intelligence than boys.
- 3) In some D.T.Ed. College the reshaw of intra and interpersonal intelligence is same in girls and boys.

Recommendation for D.T.Ed.college

- 1) Teachers in D.T.Ed. college search the type of intelligence in student and support them to learn quickly.
- 2) For interpersonal intelligence college organize co curricular activity and special teaching method.

Example: - i) Social project

ii) Collaboration work

iii) Social tour

iv) Pear Group discursion

v) Group work/project

vi) Co-operative learning, Peer Share

vii) Community project, cultural program, outdoor games etc.

3) College organizes co-curricular activity and special teaching method. for intrapersonal intelligence.

Example: - i) self-learning activities,

ii) Write a journal

iii) Individual project work

IV) Diary writing

V) Self-evaluation (SOAT)

vi) Independent research work

Vii) Meditation

viii) Project based on self-Study

ix) Self-expression.

If college organize this kind of program for development of student it support the students different intelligence they learn quickly and for longtime. Gardner also tell other 6 intelligence teachers role is to find out that intelligence in student and help him to getting quality of education and being good qualified teacher for tomorrow.

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